

Experimental Setup for CEC 2026 Competition on Benchmarking Niching Methods for Multimodal Optimization

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April 8, 2026

CIS-TF-MMO-TR-2026-001

How to cite this report:

A. Ahrari, J. E. Fieldsend, M. Preuss, X. Li, M. G. Epitropakis (2026). Experimental Setup for CEC 2026 Competition on Benchmarking Niching Methods for Multimodal Optimization. CIS-TF-MMO-TR-2026-001, IEEE CIS Task Force on Multimodal Optimization, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.19466241.

1 Introduction

The CEC 2026 competition on benchmarking niching methods for multimodal optimization (MMO)¹ employs an updated suite of composite MMO problems that was introduced in [1] and was employed as the benchmark problems for the GECCO’2024 competition on MMO [2]. This test suite has two groups of problems and eight problems in each group, resulting in a total of 16 scalable problems ($PID = 1, 2, \dots, 16$). Four dimensionalities were suggested for each problem ($D = 2, 5, 10, 20$), and each problem was generated with 15 sets of different random numbers to alleviate the effect of randomness in the problem generation process ($PIN = 1, 2, \dots, 15$). Overall, a full assessment required $16 \times 4 \times 15 = 960$ optimization runs to participate in the GECCO’2024 competition on MMO [2].

These problems simulate diverse challenges associated with MMO, including basins of different shapes, sizes, and orientations. At the same time, the convergence difficulty to global minima is varied. Moreover, the irregularity in the distribution of global minima was controlled. Nevertheless, in these problems, all variables fully interact with each other, which represents an extreme case of real-world problems rather than the average case. The new test suite aims to address this issue by defining a dependency structure. At the same time, the difficulty of convergence is reduced by 20% to shift the focus from convergence to multimodal capability.

2 Controlling Variable Interaction

The updated problems define a dependency structure for each mode. The following is an example of a dependency structure for a 5-D problem:

$$\mathcal{P} = \{[x_1, x_3], [x_2, x_5], [x_4]\}. \quad (1)$$

In this example, x_1 and x_3 interact with each other while x_2 and x_5 interact with each other. There are three blocks, and these blocks are independent, as each variable appears only in one block.

In the updated benchmarks we follow this design approach, with strictly independent blocks. The degree of interaction is therefore controlled by the number of blocks: n_{blocks} . More blocks means less interaction among variables. The average block size is D/n_{blocks} . The variation in the block sizes

¹<https://sites.google.com/view/tf-mmo/activities/competitions/mmocec2026>

is controlled by a parameter δ_{block} . For example, $\delta_{\text{block}} = 0.3$ means that the block sizes can change between 0.7 and 1.3 times the average size, which is D/n_{blocks} . A block size should of course be a positive integer number.

Once the block sizes are defined, the base dependency structure (\mathcal{P}_B) is formed by randomly assigning decision parameters to them. Dependency structures defined for each mode/basic function ($\mathcal{P}_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, N_{\text{GM}}$) is derived by perturbation of \mathcal{P}_B . This perturbation applies n_{swap} random swaps between randomly selected elements \mathcal{P}_B . Note that a swap can actually change the dependency structure if elements are selected from different blocks, and at least one block has more than one element. The dependency structures for different modes are thus not identical; however, they are not independent either as they all are formed by perturbation of one single dependency structure.

In the updated suite, n_{blocks} is proportional to the problem instance number (PIN).

$$n_{\text{blocks}} = 1 + \lceil 0.5 + \frac{PIN - 1}{PIN_{\text{max}} - 1} D \rceil, \quad PIN_{\text{max}} = 15 \quad (2)$$

in which $PIN = 1, 2, \dots, 15$. This means that for $PIN = 1$, the number of blocks is one (full interactions among decision parameters), and for the last instance, the number of blocks is D (no introduced interaction). In the latter case, if the used basic function is separable, the composite function is separable too. Methods that can learn variable interactions are expected to show better results on these test problems.

3 Experimental Setup

There are 16 parametric problems (PIDs), each with 15 instance numbers (PINs), each of which should be optimized when $D = 2, 5, 10, 20$.

3.1 Evaluation Budget

In this competition, the evaluation budget is $FE_{\text{max}} = 20,000D$, which is 60% less than the evaluation budget used in GECCO'2024 competition on MMO [2].

3.2 Performance Indicator

The overall score is the average of two indicators:

- Robust peak ratio (RPR) (see [3]): This indicator first determines peak detection accuracy (PDA) for each global minimum given $\epsilon_f = [\epsilon_f^{\text{tight}}, \epsilon_f^{\text{loose}}] = [10^{-5}, 1]$. PDA is a number in $[0, 1]$, and RPR is the average of PDAs.
- F_1 -score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. In our case, recall is equivalent to RPR, and precision is calculated as follows:

$$\textit{precision} = RPR \times N_{\text{GM}}/N_{\text{sol}} \quad (3)$$

in which N_{GM} is the number of global minima in the problem and N_{sol} is the number of reported solutions by the method as the global minima.

Each indicator is calculated for each run, and the overall score is the average of these $2 \times 960 = 1920$ numbers.

3.3 Parameter Setting

No ad-hoc tuning is allowed, and the participants should present the tuning process of their method. The following features of problems are assumed to be known a priori and can be used for parameter setting:

- problem dimensionality D ;
- search space bounds evaluation budget;
- desired tolerance for approximation of the global minimum $\epsilon_f^{\text{tight}} = 10^{-5}$, $\epsilon_f^{\text{loose}} = 10^{-1}$.

4 Using the Code

The codes of these test problems in Python and MATLAB have been provided on the competition website². See the file ‘`example1.py`’ (or ‘`example1.m`’) for a simple example explaining how to the benchmark problems. In particular you can create the problem object as follows:

²<https://sites.google.com/view/tf-mmo/activities/competitions/mmocec2026>

```
problem = ProblemMM(PID,PIN,dim)
problem.form()
```

Once the object `problem` is created and formed:

- `problem.func_eval(x)` calculates the fitness of solution(s) `x`, which can be a matrix in which each row is a solution.
- `problem.max_eval` and `problem.used_eval` return the evaluation budget and the number of calls to the function evaluations so far, respectively. (Make sure the number of used evaluations is less than or equal to the evaluation budget at the end of the optimization run.)
- `problem.low_bound` and `problem.up_bound` return the lower and upper bounds of the search space.
- `problem.dim` returns the search space dimensionality.

The file ‘`example2.py`’ (or ‘`example2.m`’) shows how RPR is calculated given the reported solutions for a typical problem.

5 Submission Instructions

The participants are encouraged to provide a PDF file describing their method. The PDF file will be uploaded to the competition website³ after the announcement of the competition outcome. If the method is already published, they can simply provide the reference.

Similar to the GECCO’2024 competition [2], a zipped folder of 960 CSV files should be provided, one CSV file for each optimization run. The name of the file should be: “`pid**_pin**_dim**.csv`”. For example, for $PID=5$, $PIN=4$, and $D = 20$, the name of the file should be “`pid05_pin04_dim20.csv`.”

Each file should contain solutions reported by the method as global optima (columns 1 to D) and their fitness values (column $D+1$). Alternatively, these solutions could be the final population if the method does not have a separate archive of reported solutions. The fitness of these solutions will be recalculated during performance assessment; therefore, solutions should be

³<https://sites.google.com/view/tf-mmo/activities/competitions/mmocec2026>

submitted with sufficiently high precision. A sample for the result files is available on the competition website.

References

- [1] A. Ahrari, J. Fieldsend, M. Preuss, X. Li, and M. Epitropakis, “New tunable test problems for benchmarking niching methods for multimodal optimization,” in *Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference*, 2024, pp. 4–12.
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